

Extensions to the WARN Associator, Integrating Magnitude Estimates based on Parameters from Unbiased Displacements

Andreas Rosenberger ^{*}, Paul Collins [†], Joe Henton [‡], Eli Ferguson [§],
Benoît Pirenne [¶], Angela Schlesinger ^{||}

V0.4, Documentation for ONC-EEW, March-July 2018, January 2019

Changes to this document

Added: Section 2.3, a redundant test for validity of seismo-geodetic PGD values. AR, 18-03-12

Changed: Some of section 2.3. Only S-wave detection and associated seismo-geodetic PGD matter here. AR, 18-03-13

Edited: Section 2.3. The time-stamps associated with seismo-geodetic PGD have to be checked. AR 18-06-12

Corrected: Error in Eq. 6.1, calculation of weights. AR, 18-07-20

Corrected: The phrasing in the 4th paragraph of the overview was ambiguous, the standard deviations are to be computed from the respective un-biased displacement time series as output by the Kalman filter. AR 19-01-12

Added: Section 2 has been broken down in two sub-sections. Section 2.1 additionally describes the use of lower bounds for the standard deviations as reported from the un-biased displacements. AR 19-01-12

1 Overview

General processing of the parameters based on observations from seismic data alone in the associator module will not change. P-wave detection times from a minimum of four stations will provide epicentre and origin time estimates, τ_P and seismic P_d reports provide initial magnitude estimates as described in Rosenberger, [2014](#).

^{*}andreas@arescon.com

[†]paul.collins@canada.ca

[‡]joe.henton@canada.ca

[§]elif@uvic.ca

[¶]bpirenne@uvic.ca

^{||}schlesin@uvic.ca

Joint processing of GNSS Precise Point Positioning (PPP) and accelerometer data by means of a Kalman filter was described in Rosenberger et al., 2017, sections 1 to 5. Section 6 describes two parameters which are derived from the resulting unbiased displacement time series:

Seismo-geodetic P_d , maximum absolute P-wave displacement from the two horizontal components observed over 5 seconds after P-wave detection

and

seismo-geodetic PGD , maximum absolute displacement from all three components, continuously updated over all phases of the seismic signal (Crowell et al., 2013).

A third important parameter, σ , generated from noise observations (in the absence of an event) of the respective *displacement* time-series is described in section 6.3 of Rosenberger et al., 2017. All three seismo-geodetic parameters are relevant during progressing phases of an ensuing earthquake for continuously updating magnitude estimates which can be reported to client systems as they become available.

Since three different PPP time-series, based on broadcast orbits (B), floating-point ambiguity resolution (F) and integer ambiguity resolution (I) exist, a total of three parameter pairs are reported from seismo-geodetic observations at different times during an earthquake from the on-site systems:

Five seconds after P-wave detection

1. P_d^B, σ^B
2. P_d^F, σ^F
3. P_d^I, σ^I

From the time of the detection of P- or S-wave arrival, updated in one second time intervals

1. PGA^B, σ^B
2. PGA^F, σ^F
3. PGA^I, σ^I

where the respective σ for each group are actually identical since they were generated from the same *displacement* data immediately before the event. In the following those σ values are regarded as proxies describing the reliability of the associated displacement observation and *the objective is to propagate those into final uncertainties in the seismo-geodetic magnitude estimates*. Rather than initially choosing the apparently best solution from broadcast orbit, floating-point- or integer ambiguity resolution based displacements it is suggested to use the concept of *weighted averages* (Taylor, 1997) instead.

2 Validating seismo-geodetic parameters

2.1 Additional lower error bounds

First recorded data from small earthquakes have shown that the standard deviations σ computed from 600 seconds of unbiased displacement data before the detection of the event may under-estimate the overall uncertainty in the Kalman filter output. In particular the time series depending on broadcast orbit corrections may be affected by fluctuations with longer periods.

It is therefore suggested that a more representative quantization of potential error is established from direct observations over the network of stations and over a longer period of time. Samples of unbiased displacement data are available with the one second heart-beat messages from the seismo-geodetic stations. Computing their standard deviations Σ in the absence of earthquakes over a longer period of time (a day or even longer) would help to establish *lower* bounds Σ^B , Σ^F , Σ^I on the errors in displacements for each of the broadcast orbits, floatingpoint- and integer-ambiguity solutions. The respective σ would then be established as

$$\sigma^B = \max(\Sigma^B, \sigma^B)$$

$$\sigma^F = \max(\Sigma^F, \sigma^F)$$

$$\sigma^I = \max(\Sigma^I, \sigma^I)$$

Using the pre-established (and periodically updated) Σ as parameters in the Associator would effectively guard against anomalous short-time, small standard deviations as they may be determined by the procedure outlined in Rosenberger et al., 2017, section 6.3 and would also more efficiently assure that anomalous peak displacements are down-weighted in the weighted average computations described in section 3.

2.2 Signal to Noise Ratio Threshold

The respective σ for each of the B-, F- and I PPP time-series can be interpreted as the current (pre-event) RMS noise level of the respective unbiased displacement time series. Observations then qualify as *valid* if they exceed a certain signal to noise ratio (S/N):

$$P > S \cdot \sigma, \tag{2.1}$$

here P and σ stand for any of the observation pairs described above and S is the *minimum acceptable signal to noise ratio*. Any reported displacement below the minimum S/N ratio should be discarded and it will be quite common with smaller earthquakes that none of the initial seismo-geodetic P_d values will pass this test. This may also be true for the later, normally larger PGD from a mid magnitude earthquake in a larger distance from the reporting station.

S should be seen as a global parameter, it is not station dependent. Suggested is a value of $S = 3.0$ for initial tests but we may have to change it.

2.3 Plausibility of seismo-geodetic PGD

The current version of the Associator/Correlator from the WARN project will verify P-wave detections and the associated parameters based on timestamps matching P-wave travel-times from a given epicentre and origin time.

This leaves parameters associated with detection of the S-wave arrival, here seismo-geodetic PGD, to be checked if their timestamps are consistent with origin time and S-wave travel-time to the respective station.

It cannot be ruled out that a station starts to report valid (in the sense of the test in eq. 2.1) PGD values if seismic waveform processing has detected a spurious S-wave (a false trigger). The timestamps t of the reported $PGD(t)$ values for a given earthquake should satisfy:

$$t \geq t_0 + R/S_v \quad (2.2)$$

here t_0 is origin time, R distance of the station from the epicentre in km and S_v is the average S-wave propagation velocity, $S_v = 3.6km/s$ (Crowell et al., 2016, they use a $3.0km/s$ travel-time mask). $PGD(t)$ reports with time-stamps t later then the maximum observation time interval $t \geq t_0 + T_{obs}$ should also be discarded (suggested are $T_{obs} = 200s$ in Rosenberger et al., 2017).

3 Combining observed parameters from the three different seismo-geodetic displacement time series

Any observation in the P_d or PGD groups passing the test in equations 2.1 (and 2.2) can then be used to compute a *weighted* average (Taylor, 1997). With weights

$$w_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \quad (3.1)$$

the weighted average becomes

$$\bar{P} = \frac{\sum w_i P_i}{\sum w_i} \quad (3.2)$$

assuming that more than one P observation was validated. Here again P stands for either P_d or PGD , σ is the respective standard deviation, the index i stands for any of the B, F, or I derived displacements or standard deviations.

The standard deviation of the *weighted* average \bar{P} then becomes

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum w_i}} \quad (3.3)$$

For example, the three P_d reports from one station are combined as

$$\bar{P}_d = \frac{w_B P_d^B + w_F P_d^F + w_I P_d^I}{w_B + w_F + w_I} \quad (3.4)$$

with $w_B = \frac{1}{\sigma^2_B}$, $w_F = \frac{1}{\sigma^2_F}$, $w_I = \frac{1}{\sigma^2_I}$

and the standard deviation of $\overline{P_d}$ is

$$\overline{\sigma_{P_d}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{w_B + w_F + w_I}} \quad (3.5)$$

The concept of using a weighted average from broadcast orbits, floating-point and integer ambiguity resolution based observations still needs to be confirmed experimentally. It is not yet clear if certain conditions with the GNSS correction data and PPP algorithms may limit its performance.

4 Single Station Magnitude Estimates based on $\overline{P_d}$ and $\overline{\sigma_{P_d}}$

The reported P_d value from a single station depends on the distance R from the epicentre. The following is thus based on the assumption that more than three stations have reported P-wave detection times, an epicentre was established and that the validation process and subsequent computation of *weighted* averages from a station report has yielded a pair of $\overline{P_d}$, $\overline{\sigma}$ values.

Crowell et al., 2013 give the magnitude scaling relationship for $\overline{P_d}$ in centimeters and distance R in kilometers as

$$M_{\overline{P_d}} = \frac{\log(\overline{P_d}) + A + C \log(R)}{B} \quad (4.1)$$

with

$$A = 0.893, B = 0.562, C = 1.731$$

and $\log()$ the base 10 logarithm.

The standard deviation of $\overline{P_d}$, $\overline{\sigma_{P_d}}$ (eq. 3.5), is propagated through the corresponding error propagation law to quantify the uncertainty in the magnitude estimate:

$$\sigma_{M_{\overline{P_d}}} = \frac{d}{d\overline{P_d}} M(\overline{P_d}) \cdot \overline{\sigma_{P_d}} = \frac{1}{\ln(10) B \overline{P_d}} \cdot \overline{\sigma_{P_d}}, \quad (4.2)$$

here $\ln()$ is the natural logarithm.

5 Single Station Magnitude Estimates based on \overline{PGD} and $\overline{\sigma_{PGD}}$

A similar procedure as in section 4 applies here. PGD (in cm) is also dependent on the distance R (km) from the epicentre. Crowell et al., 2013 found the empirical relationship

$$M_{PGD} = \frac{\log(\overline{PGD}) + D}{E - F \log(R)} \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 1: Seismo-geodetic P_d scaling relationships for mid-size to large earthquake magnitudes (after Crowell et al., 2013). Note, that for an $M_w 5$ earthquake the limits of resolution of the seismo-geodetic system ($\sigma \approx 1\text{cm}$, thick black line) are reached at a hypo-central distance of about 10 km.

with

$$D = 5.013, E = 1.219, F = 0.178$$

the corresponding error propagation relationship is

$$\sigma_{M_{PPGD}} = \frac{dM(\overline{P_{PGD}})}{dP_{PGD}} \cdot \sigma_{PGD} = \frac{\sigma_{PGD}}{P_{PGD} \cdot \ln(10) \cdot (E - F \log(R))} \quad (5.2)$$

$\ln()$ again being the natural logarithm.

Figure 2: Seismo-geodetic PGD magnitude scaling relationships for mid-size to large earthquake magnitudes (aft. Crowell et al., 2013). The limits of resolution for the seismo-geodetic system ($\sigma \approx 1$ cm, thick black line) are reached for $M_w 5$ at a hypo-central distance of about 10 km, for $M_w 6$ at about 100 km.

6 Multi Station Magnitude Estimates

As soon as estimates of M_{P_d} and its corresponding $\sigma_{M_{P_d}}$ from multiple stations (i.e. more than one) have become available, the same *weighted* average computation can yield an update for a general magnitude estimate and its estimated error:

With weights

$$w_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_{M_i}^2} \quad (6.1)$$

the actual magnitude estimate becomes

$$\bar{M} = \frac{\sum w_i \cdot \bar{M}_i}{\sum w_i} \quad (6.2)$$

the uncertainty

$$\bar{\sigma}_M = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum w_i}} \quad (6.3)$$

As instrument sites update their *PGD* observations in one second time intervals over the full observation time interval (suggested are 200 seconds in Rosenberger et al., 2017) the calculations from section 5 and 6.1 to 6.3 have to be performed for each incoming *PGD* update in the same way.

Reports to downstream client systems would then give magnitude as $\bar{M} \pm \bar{\sigma}_M$.

7 Transition from seismic only to seismo-geodetic Magnitude predictions

As discussed above, for most small to moderate size earthquakes seismo-geodetic magnitude estimates will not become available, simply because seismo-geodetic P_d and also *PGD* will fail the signal to noise ratio test in 2.1. Magnitudes will then be reported solely based on seismic τ_p and P_d as described in Rosenberger, 2014.

However, as soon as more than three seismo-geodetic magnitude estimates are available *and* the associated uncertainty $\bar{\sigma}_M$ is smaller than 0.5 magnitude units reporting should switch to seismo-geodetic magnitudes and no longer report magnitudes based on seismic P_d and τ_p .

This needs further discussion.

8 Summary, Discussion

Comparing the seismo-geodetic *PGD* (fig. 2) with the seismic only P_d scaling relationship (fig. 8) it appears that only for earthquakes with magnitude $M > 6.0$ seismo-geodetic *PGD* scaling becomes relevant and would supersede seismic only P_d and τ_p based estimates. This would involve stations within about 100km distance from the epicentre and with the planned network configuration likely more than

Figure 3: Seismic-only P_d magnitude scaling relationships for mid-size to large earthquake magnitudes (aft. Kuyuk and Allen, 2013). Assuming a sensitivity in respect to displacements better than 0.1cm , a $M > 5.0$ earthquake would likely produce a magnitude estimate from stations in less than 10km distance, a magnitude $M > 6.0$ would likely trigger reports from stations within about 100km distance.

three. However, seismo-geodetic PGD will come into play at a much later time since it involves the observation of later seismic phases.

Note, that for an instrument in 100km distance it would likely need a $M > 7.0$ to produce a seismo-geodetic P_d based estimate (see fig. 1).

Initially magnitude estimates would thus have to rely on seismic observations from the P-wave arrivals only, and as soon as at least three PGD based estimates are available, only those would be reported.

For earthquakes with magnitudes larger than $M7.5$ seismo-geodetic P_d comes into play much earlier for stations within 100km of the epicentre and the transition from seismic only to seismo-geodetic magnitudes would thus take place as soon as the first three seismo-geodetic P_d reports are available.

References

- Crowell, Brendan W. et al. (2013). “Earthquake magnitude scaling using seismogeodetic data”. In: *GRL* 40, 60896094. DOI: [10.1002/2013GL058391](https://doi.org/10.1002/2013GL058391).
- Crowell, Brendan W. et al. (2016). “Demonstration of the Cascadia G-FAST Geodetic Earthquake Early Warning System for the Nisqually, Washington, Earthquake”. In: *SRL* 87, pp. 930–943. DOI: [10.1785/0220150255](https://doi.org/10.1785/0220150255).
- Kuyuk, H.S. and R.M. Allen (2013). “A Global Approach to Provide Magnitude Estimates for Earthquake Early Warning Alerts”. In: *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 40.24, 63296333. DOI: [10.1002/2013GL058580](https://doi.org/10.1002/2013GL058580).
- Rosenberger, Andreas (2014). *Three component accelerometer signal processing for WARN*. Tech. rep. Ocean Networks Canada, University of Victoria.
- Rosenberger, Andreas et al. (2017). *Kalman Filter Algorithm for the joint Processing of GNSS PPP and Accelerometer Data and EEW parameters from the unbiased displacement time-series*. Tech. rep. ONC, University of Victoria.
- Taylor, John R. (1997). *An Introduction to Error Analysis*. Ed. by Ann McGuire. 2nd Edition. University Science Books.